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Research Ethics: The Bane of the unethical researcher

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Every human research creates generalizable information which is an integral part of health improvement & understanding of disease. It also causes some risk or inconvenience to research participants. Codes of conduct for physicians have existed since ancient period. Declaration of Helsinki

ICMR, Human subjects' protection; Animal care guidelines etc provide a policy for conduct of research involving research participants in India. The Why & the How in research are vital questions. The 'Why' is very clear to define as improvement of public health. What matters more is the 'How': while performing it is necessary to adhere to research ethics for promotion of knowledge, truth and avoidance of errors. Research being team work, involves principles of team work such as trust, mutual respect, even handedness, and accountability. Upholding confidentiality, data sharing policies, guidelines of authorship, peer review policies, copyright and patenting policy promotes security of intellectual property and gives confidence for collaborations. Ethical research outlines standard guidelines for institutions and professionals for their behavior towards the specified goals and helps to develop the trust of community further promoting funding.

Maintaining dignity, rights, safety & well-being of research participants is mandatory to every researcher. Autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence & justice are four primary principles which can be further elaborated on various aspects of research. Research ethics related to participants are essentialities like ensuring privacy & confidentiality, voluntariness, minimum risks & maximum benefits and non-exploitation. Research ethics related to researchers are transparency, accountability, maintenance of fair professional competence & institutional arrangements, taking total responsibility including social & environmental protection.

Ethics is multidimensional but crucial to maintain research integrity. Medical professionals have always enjoyed high regards from the society & have got easy access to confidential information with less accountability. Erosion of general ethics inclusive of research ethics in society has greatly increased. Easy accessibility & possibility of manipulations due to trust have resulted in history of research misconduct involving not only harm but also death at times. Research misconduct misleading to readers is not only a threat to the present generation but also to all generations of mankind. The common practices of research misconduct are plagiarism, falsification, fabrication, publication malpractices & conflict of interest. This may be done under the pressure from the funder, for the most part pharmaceutical companies or other reasons of conflicts of interest.

The publication & authorship malpractices (3Gs: Ghost, Gift and Guest authorship) have strongly emerged after its application criteria for academic promotion. All academicians may not have interest in research or writing skills required for manuscript writing. Considering only one aspect, i.e. publication, other than educational qualifications may force a vulnerable academician to research misconduct due to insecurity of sustaining present position or strong urge of getting to a higher position without healthy competition. The other aspects such as educational scholarships, administrative responsibilities, teaching scholarships can be included as part of evaluation for academic promotions.

Males due to their roles in family, social dynamics & performance pressure are affected easily.

Researchers who are unethical & are at higher positions are great threat to research integrity. They imbibe unethical practices in younger professionals & demotivate the ethical

person. Fairness, and professionalism remain at risk & raising one's voice becomes more difficult against them. At present whistle-blowers cannot be anonymous & that may be reason for underreporting of misconduct. They try to manipulate the system at institute level, publishing erroneous results and affecting society at large.

It has been observed that many institutes have more than one institutional ethics committee (IEC) or review boards (IRB). Formation of all of them should abide the rules of IEC or IRB formation. Otherwise, most committees other than primary IEC which are not as per guidelines are possibly lean to indulge practices of plagiarism. Regular trainings to scrutinize with stringent rules can be taken into consideration by regulatory bodies. IEC needs to be strong and should abide by all rules with interference in unethical practices in the institutes. Institutional regulatory bodies should strictly follow up all research till its publication & take actions against unethical practices even with anonymous complaint if found credible. Rights of researchers & participants must be protected and scrutiny of responsibilities of researcher during the conduct of research shall be evaluated by 360⁰ feedbacks, anonymous feedback from all stakeholders.

Primary responsibility of investigations of misconduct lies with institutes. Very often the mild penalties such as correction of research data do not act as a sufficient deterrent. It just dilutes the impact of misconduct. A harsher penalty would make an unethically inclined researcher to think hard and long before indulging in such malpractices and would act as a morale booster for those working sincerely and conscientiously.

Values, morals & ethics get inculcated in any person from their childhood. There is an innate nature or personality trait of researchers, his/ her upbringing and impact of early childhood experiences from family & society which influences the person's ethical values. Rather, a professional researcher at the start of his career has already developed his values & ethics where it further gets modified by research culture where he works. Research misconduct hinders the good research culture. Often these malpractices are carried over into medical practice further eroding the confidence in our profession. It is the responsibility of the researcher to conduct the research ethically & legally. Every researcher should become familiar with Good Clinical Practices (GCP) and each institute should have local regulatory policy to ensure appropriate research culture. Early interventions about research ethics are needed; it can be as early as during bachelor's degree and reinforcement by research ethics trainings may ensure its awareness among researchers but doubtful about inculcation of the same in the researcher. Inculcating research ethics promotes social and moral value development such as responsibilities towards human & animal protection, legality & public safety.

I believe that strong research ethics regulations are the need of the hour to ensure clean and unbiased studies to help bring back the confidence in their conclusions as also to help restore the medical profession to some of its former adulation.